

ISic2709

I.Sicily inscription 2709

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (white)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana (?)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 139

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332692

1. [έκοιμήθη έ]ν πίστι κ (αί) ειρήνη
2. [ό δεΐνα] δοϋλος τοϋ θ (εο) υ̅ ,
3. [τῆ πρὸ — — Κα] λ(ανδῶν) #⁵⁶ Ἰουλίωv
4. [ύπατία Σεβήρ]ου κ (αί) Ἰωρδανίου
5. [έγεν(ήθη) υπό Θε]οδοσίου τὸ γ.
- 6.

Edition: PHI334899

1. [έκοιμήθη έ] ν πίστι κ (αί) ειρήνη
2. [(nomen)] δοϋλος τοϋ θ (εο) υ̅
3. [τῆ πρὸ — κα] λ(ανδῶν) Ἰουλίωv
4. [ύπατία Σεβήρ]ου κ (αί) Ἰωρδανίου
5. [έγενν(ήθη) ύπατία Θ] εοδοσίου τὸ γ.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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PHI 334899

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